

РОЗРОБЛЕННЯ СИСТЕМИ УПРАВЛІННЯ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЄЮ

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE ORGANIZATIONAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Management is the control over the effective and efficient regulation and implementation of the structure and constituent elements of an organization enterprise.

Management is a multifaceted process that includes the existence of companies, their position in the market, development dynamics, competitiveness, and timely identification of risks, and its goal is to ensure financial stability, form its own brand in production services and other sectors and to obtain high income with limited resources.

Management also includes establishing the structure of an organization, enterprise and its constituent elements, formulating its strategy and the level of its implementation, the effective and efficient distribution of available resources between departments and divisions indicators of achieving the company's strategic goals and monitoring the overall process by determining the quality coefficient of employee performance.

Figure 1. The current problems in the management of organization include.

For organization to develop and operate successfully, it is essential to address

the above-mentioned problems, if they exist. The role of the human resources department in the management and development of organization is indispensable.

Human resources is a structural unit of an enterprise or organization responsible for the implementation and management of employee recruitment, adaptation, employee performance evaluation, identification of potential, identification of training needs, salary and promotion, and other procedures.

There are important points to pay attention to when managing organizations. These include the following:

1. Instilling the specific values of the enterprise in employees and forming an ethical and cultural work environment;
2. Strengthening cooperation with employees of other structural divisions of the organization and their managers;
3. Have superior creativity and problem-solving skills;
4. Understanding the institution as a concept and understanding that one is a part of this concept;
5. Having the ability and potential to change behavior and abilities;
6. Having the power to influence managers and employees in decision-making in other necessary situations;
7. Anticipating the necessary change needs of the enterprise and adapting flexibly to changes; [1, p 14].

The attitude of managers towards employees directly affects the development of management policies of organizations.

Figure 2. Forms of attitude towards work [4, p. 39].

The common features for the companies currently leading the market are:

1. Healthy competitive business environment
2. Successfully organized management policy
3. Corporate culture friendly and welcoming work environment
4. Fair evaluation system
5. Valuing employees' work
6. Investing in training and development
7. Competent visionary experienced and leadership having quality managers

and leaders.

The benefits of effective staff management for businesses are:

1. Leading to a reduction in labour costs.
2. Minimizing errors and accidents during the execution of tasks and tasks.
3. Resulting in an increase in employee morale.
4. Reducing legal risks.
5. Increasing customer satisfaction indicators. [3]

Talent champions- this term refers to individuals who invest time and effort in discovering hidden talents in the workplace and improving their skills.

Figure 3.Types of employees [2, p. 36].

Conclusion and suggestions.

1. A proper management policy must be established for the development and successful operation of enterprises and organizations.

2. Coordination between organization and structural units and departments is essential.
3. Recruitment policies should be improved, and skilled, competent, and fair recruiters should be attracted to enterprises and organizations.
4. The number of managers with leadership qualities should be increased.
5. Employees' work should be fairly evaluated and they should be involved in necessary training, development their knowledge and skills, reveal their hidden potential, and organize motivational events.
6. Clear and realistic goals should be set, and when setting goals for employees, they should be approached individually and set goals that are in line with their potential. Otherwise, they will not be able to overcome unrealistic goals, which can demotivate them and prevent them developing.
7. Interpersonal relationships (respect, value, empathy) and a health and friendly work environment should be created. Conflicts and problems should be resolved in a timely manner.

References

1. Aliyev M., Hamidov H. Human Resources Management in Business, Textbook, Baku : "Iqtisad University" Publishing House, 2013. 532 p.
2. Andy Cross. Talent Management Pocketbook, 2016. 112 p.
3. <https://www.myob.com/au/insight/post/workforce-management?srsltid=AfmBOoqWLEh0XfmntuwVU5iXG2Ca0JbvWyGw3SB3K3all2yuCTClhNu>.
4. Working Relationship Pocketbook, Fiona Elsa Dent, 2009. 112 p.